

TIL, TA'LIM, TARJIMA ЯЗЫК, ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ, ПЕРЕВОД LANGUAGE, EDUCATION, TRANSLATION

TILSHUNOSLIK

Атаджанова Рохатой Бутанбаевна

Старший преподаватель, кафедра общих дисциплин
Янгиерский филиал Ташкентского
химико-технологического университета
г. Янгиер, Узбекистан

УНИВЕРСАЛЬНОСТЬ И СПЕЦИФИЧНОСТЬ ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНЫХ ТЕРМИНОВ: ЛИНГВИСТИЧЕСКИЙ АСПЕКТ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В статье рассматривается комплекс лингвистически релевантных характеристик, присущих профессиональным терминологическим единицам независимо от сферы или сферы их применения. В статье ставится задача исследовать лингвистические особенности терминов через призму некоторых экстралингвистических факторов, которые всегда сопутствуют лингвистическим. Автор статьи постарался охватить все сферы и дать общие характеристики. Таким образом, статья носит обзорный характер с целью исследования природы термина и его существенных признаков в представленном онтогенезе. В статье подчеркивается значимость любого исследования терминологических единиц с точки зрения когнитивных исследований, поскольку оно показывает понимание автором понятий «термин» и «терминологическая система». В статье глубоко и детально исследуются такие характерные признаки терминов и терминологических единиц, как ограниченность сферы употребления, соотнесенность с определенным специальным понятием, условность, системная принадлежность, стилистическая нейтральность, моносемичность, мотивированность. Кроме того, автором учитываются и второстепенные

характерные признаки, такие как современность, звучность, интернациональность, номинация.

Ключевые слова: термин; терминосистема; терминология; прагматика; функциональный подход; субстанциональный подход; характеристика термина.

Atajanova Roxatoy Butanbaevna
Katta o'qituvchi, "Umumiy fanlar" kafedrasida
Toshkent kimyo-texnologiya
universiteti Yangiyer filiali
Yangiyer sh., O'zbekiston

KASBIY TERMINLARNING UNIVERSALLIGI VA XUSUSIYATLARI: LINGVISTIK ASPEKTI

ANNOTATSIYA

Maqolada kasbiy terminologik birliklarga xos bo'lgan lingvistik ahamiyatga ega xususiyatlar va ularni aniq bir sohada yoki umumiy vaziyatlarda ishlatilishi ko'rib chiqiladi. Maqola atamalarning lingvistik xususiyatlarini har doim lingvistik omillar bilan birga keladigan ba'zi ekstralingvistik omillar prizmasi orqali o'rganishga qaratilgan. Maqolaning muallifi barcha sohalarni qamrab olishga va umumiy xususiyatlarni belgilashga harakat qildi. Shunday qilib, tadqiqot atamaning tabiatini va taqdim etilgan ontogenezdagi uning muhim xususiyatlarini o'rganish maqsadida sharh shaklida olib bo'rilgan. Kognitiv tadqiqotlar nuqtai nazaridan terminologik birliklardagi har qanday tadqiqotning ahamiyati katta va bu nazar ushbu maqolada ham ta'kidlab o'tilgan. Maqolada atamalar va terminologik birliklarning qo'llanish doirasining chegaralanishi, ma'lum bir maxsus tushuncha bilan bog'liqligi, an'anaviylik, tizim aksessuari, uslubiy neytrallik, monosemik xususiyat, motivatsiya kabi asosiy xususiyatlari chuqur va batafsil o'rganiladi. Bundan tashqari, muallif tomonidan zamonaviylik, jadallik, xalqarolik va nominatsiya kabi qo'shimcha xususiyatlar ham hisobga olinadi.

Kalit so'zlar: atamalar; terminologik tizim; terminologiya; pragmatika; funktsional yondashuv; kognitiv yondashuv; atama xususiyatlari.

Atadjanova Rokhatoy Butanbaevna
Senior Teacher, Department of General Disciplines
Yangiyer branch of Tashkent
Chemical-Technological University
Yangiyer City, Uzbekistan

UNIVERSALITY AND SPECIFICITY OF PROFESSIONAL TERMS: LINGUISTIC ASPECT

ABSTRACT

The paper considers the complex of linguistically relevant characteristics inherent in professional terminological units, regardless of the field or area of their implementation. The article aims to research linguistic features of terms through a prism of some extralinguistic factors that always come along with linguistic ones. The author of the paper tried to cover all spheres and define general characteristics. Thus, the article took the form of review with the purpose to investigate the nature of a term and its salient characteristics in the provided ontogenesis. The significance of any research in terminological units from the point of view of the cognitive studies is underlined in this paper as it shows the author's understanding of the concepts of «term» and «terminological system». Such characteristic features of terms and terminological units as limitation of the usage sphere, correlation to a certain special concept, conventionality, system accessory, stylistic neutrality, monosemic feature, and motivation are investigated deeply and in details in the paper. In addition, minor characteristic features, such as the modernity, sonority, internationality, and nomination are also taken into consideration by the author.

Keywords: terms; terminological system; terminology; pragmatics; functional approach; substantive approach; term characterization.

Introduction. Living in the era of total globalization, which causes the rapid growth of information and communication technologies, the emergence of new geo-economic challenges, political and economic cultural integration, we are witnessing the rapid growth and constant replenishment of the corpus of scientific terms in various fields of knowledge, which have a clear tendency to further increase in volume [1, 363]. That is why, within the framework of the modern science of language, interest in studying the patterns and features of the formation, formation and subsequent development of terminological systems does not fade away. Such a complex of geopolitical and global economic characteristics of modern society substantiates the urgent need for a thorough study of various areas of theoretical and practical terminology and lexicography. So, we consider it expedient to consider the basic concepts of modern terminology and the main approaches to understanding the essence of the term, the relationship between the concepts of "term", "terminology" and "terminal system", as well as to identify a set of common characteristics of terminological units that have undoubted linguistic significance.

Methodology of the Research. The problem of studying special vocabulary and, in particular, terminology is one of the urgent and important tasks of linguistics today. Terms are studied within a separate branch of linguistics - terminology. Modern terminology is an interdisciplinary discipline that studies the semantic basis and grammatical laws of the functioning of terms and terminological systems of various branches of an individual's activity.

Literature Review. To date, there is an impressive number of scientific works that explore the concept of "term", analyze the content of this concept, consider its functions, as well as lexical-semantic, pragma-communicative and cognitive-

discursive characteristics. Back in the 1970s, A.D. Khayutin considered the idea of creating a new scientific discipline – terminology [cited in: 3, 12]. Based on the results of the research, scientists identified 3 main directions for the development of this scientific area: terminological proper (within which, on the basis of general linguistic laws and principles, specific characteristics of terminology as a system are determined and analyzed); terminographic (in fact, contrastive studies are being carried out, the main purpose of which is to compile and improve industry-specific terminological dictionaries); terminology (carrying out private linguistic studies of specific terms and/or term systems on the actual material of individual branches of knowledge and/or individual languages).

First of all, it is necessary to consider some theoretical issues in the field of terminology, in particular, to study what a term is and what characteristics it has.

Despite the earlier conduct of a number of studies in the framework of working with the terms of various fields of science and technology, great interest in terminology and its methods of analysis arose precisely in the 50s-60s of the XX century, as evidenced by the appearance of numerous works of linguists in this field. In the circle of scientists dealing with the problems of terminology, the works of A.A. Reformatsky, in which the fundamental principles of domestic terminology were laid [cited in: 3, 14]. In his opinion, terms are words limited by their specific purpose, and tending to be unambiguous for the exact expression of the concepts and naming of things and phenomena of reality. “Terms exist not just in the language, but as part of a certain terminology” [cited in: 3, 16].

Discussion and Results. The complex nature of the term causes interest in the problems of terminology and the existence of various approaches to the definition of this concept. Some researchers derive a sufficient logical definition of the term "term", while others strive for a descriptive disclosure of the content of the concept, while taking into account its characteristic features. For a long time, the status of the term had a rather debatable character [5, 28]. Attempts were made both to bring the terms out of the language by opposing them to the commonly used layer of vocabulary, and to identify them with each other. However, disputes regarding this opposition began to gradually lose their relevance, which, first of all, is connected with the understanding of the term as a word (or phrase), inextricably linked with the concept and belonging to a particular field of knowledge or activity.

According to E.I. Golovanova, all the originality of the terminological unit lies precisely in its structure, i.e. its internal semantic organization: “The specificity of a term lies not in terms of expression, but in terms of content, in the nature of its meaning” [7, 38]. The originality of the term is that the term is a word to which one or another definition associated with a scientific concept is artificially, consciously attributed.

V.P. Danilenko and T.L. Kandelaki agree in the definition of the term, according to which it is a word or phrase (in the definition of T.L. Kandelaki - “lexicalized phrase”), which belongs to a special sphere of use and is the name of a

special concept, and also requires a definition to establish its meaning in the corresponding system concepts [9, 71; 10, 94].

Analyzing the whole variety of formulations of the concept under consideration, it can be stated that there are at least two points of view regarding the definition of the nature of the term: substantial and functional. According to the adherents of the substantive approach, terms are special words and phrases that have characteristic features: monosemantics, accuracy, consistency, contextual independence and emotional neutrality, etc.

Nevertheless, it is well known that not all terms can satisfy the totality of these characteristics. For this reason, many terminologists are critical of the interpretations of the term introduced by the proponents of the substantive approach. Some linguists tend to take a functional approach to the essence of a term.

So, A.Yu. Bagiyan gives the following definition of the nature of a term: "Any word can act as a term... Terms are not special words, but words in a special function" [2, 257]. This point of view is also shared by K.Ya. Averbukh [3] and S.V. Grinev-Grinevich [8].

A rather capacious definition is given by L.A. Kapanadze [11, 86], T.D. Mikhaylenko [12, 49] and S.D. Shelov [15, 795], according to which the term is a special word (or phrase) adopted in the framework of professional activity and used in special conditions; verbal designation of a concept included in the general system of concepts of a certain area of professional knowledge; the main conceptual element of the language for special purposes (LSP = Language for Special Purposes), which requires a special definition (exact scientific definition) for its adequate understanding. In our opinion, this definition most accurately reflects the essence of the term "term" and makes it possible to understand both its nature and functionality.

In the case of the definition of the definition of the key concept for our study "term", we think it is right to consider the definitions of some foreign scientists. While most domestic researchers consider a term as a word or phrase, British and American colleagues admit the possibility of the existence of terms in the form of abbreviations, individual letters and even symbols. This is evidenced, for example, by the following definition given by A.Yu. Bagiyan: a term is a linguistic symbol associated with one or more concepts, which, in turn, are defined with the help of related concepts [6, 199]. A term can thus be represented as a word or phrase, as well as a letter or graphic symbol, abbreviation, acronym, symbol, and the like. A similar point of view is shared by I.A. Rebrushkina and O.L. Ariskina, arguing that a term is a linguistic sign that expresses a special concept and reflects the place it occupies in the corresponding system of concepts [14, 208].

In connection with the dominant anthropocentric paradigm in modern linguistics, we consider it appropriate to consider the concept of a term also from the standpoint of cognitive science, namely, cognitive terminology. In this vein, the point of view of E.I. Golovanova, according to which the term is nothing more than a verbalized result of professional thinking, a significant linguo-cognitive means of orientation in the professional sphere and the most important element of professional

communication [7]. It is also worth noting that the cognitive component permeates the entire complex of structural and semantic characteristics of terminological units of any field of activity and field of knowledge, since the phenomenon of thinking is unified for each individual, regardless of the type of his activity.

S.D. Shelov in his work "Once again on the definition of the concept of "term", to clarify the nature of the concept of "term", analyzes thirty definitions of the "term", as a result of which he proposes his own definition: the term is a linguistic sign (which can be represented by a word, a phrase, a combination of the word or phrases with special symbols, etc.), expressing the concept of a certain field of knowledge and having a definition (interpretation, explanation), which, in turn, is consciously oriented by those who use this linguistic sign [15, 796].

Based on the previously presented definitions of the concept of "term", we offer our own formulation of this phenomenon, taking into account the opinions of both domestic and foreign colleagues: the term is a special language unit, which is a verbalized result of professional thinking, which can be expressed as a symbol, abbreviation, words or phrases; this linguistic unit is often monosemic, has a strict definition and is limited to a special area of use.

Having decided on the concept of "term" and the complex nature of its definition, we consider it appropriate to specify the coordinate system of this study by clarifying the wording of the concepts of "terminology" and "terminal system".

The terms of a certain special area in their totality form the terminology of this area. The terms are characterized by spontaneity and inconsistency of formation, and are also formed in accordance with various cognitive and structural models of the nomination. The term is the main element of the terminological system.

Consideration of the terminology makes it possible to trace the stages of development of the corresponding special sphere. Terminology is often considered from a diachronic point of view, since it is possible to single out primary terms, terms of historicism and archaisms, neologism terms.

Terminology ordered according to some criteria forms a terminological system, or a terminological system.

So, we come to a comparison of the concepts of "terminology" and "terminology". In this case, the opinions of scientists also differ, which is absolutely justified, because the concepts under consideration are directly related to the phenomenon of the term, the nature and definitional status of which, in turn, are also dualistic.

There is a point of view of T.D. Mikhaylenko [13], in relation to which no field of knowledge and / or branch of activity can have a random chaotic accumulation of terms that would be systemically unrelated and unorganized, because everything that displays and serves a certain terminology in the world is systemic, just as the world itself is systemic. In accordance with this statement, the concepts of "terminology" and "terminological system" are synonymous and denote a system of signs of a certain special field of knowledge and / or sphere of activity

of an individual, relatively isomorphic to the system of its concepts, serving its communicative needs.

However, we tend to adhere to the opinion that modern terminology distinguishes two similar and related, but nevertheless independent and largely autonomous types of terminological sets that function in special sublanguages - terminology and terminological system. The first phenomenon is characterized by a spontaneously formed set of terminological units, while the second is presented as a consciously formed set of terms.

The presented difference between the concepts under consideration is manifested in a significant number of aspects, including the cognitive component. It is logical that the spontaneous formation of terminology leads to a not quite adequate reflection of a certain special field of knowledge, since the terms included in a certain terminology may not have signs of consistency and have inaccurate units in terms of motivation and semantics.

So, "terminology as a set of industry terms goes through a long path of formation and transformation into a terminological system."

Often this process coincides with the period of formation of a correlating field of knowledge, as R.Sh. Akhmedov shows in his article [4]. It follows from this that not all industry terminologies can be gradually transformed into term systems as a more highly organized element of the term system. The completion of this process of terminology formation and its transformation into a terminology system will mean the onset of a period of relative stabilization of the system, as well as the fact that the vast majority of phenomena in a special sphere will be consistently nominated (described) by this set of terminological units.

This point of view is also confirmed by the works of A. Yu. Bagiyan, who argue that if terminology is a real object that models the real picture of the subject area in dynamics, then the term system is always a model of terminology, its formalized description. The term system, in this case, can be defined as a cognitive model of terminology, or a metamodel of a certain subject area [5, 30].

In our opinion, the terminological system is a kind of synchronous slice of terminology, i.e. a certain set of terms, ordered into a system, taking into account certain logical relationships, imprinted in a certain period of time.

Thus, guided by a clearly defined system of coordinates of our study, as well as based on the above definitions and opinions of authoritative domestic and foreign linguists, as well as our definitions of the concepts of "term" and "terminal system", we denote the main linguistically relevant characteristics of terminological units:

1. Monosemy. This characteristic is also defined as "content accuracy" or "term semantic accuracy". The term in its ideal version should have only one meaning in a single language and a certain special field of knowledge; it is not publicly available, but is used by specialists working within the special field in which the term functions.

2. System affiliation. This characteristic is directly related to the term system concept and denotes the perception of the term in its direct relationship with other specialized terminological units with which it has a close relationship.

3. Correlation with a certain special concept. Terms have a strict definition, which facilitates the perception and understanding of the term, they can denote a specific object, phenomenon, process or abstract concept. The term is reasonably interpreted as the name of the concept.

4. Limited scope of use. Within the framework of the Yangiyer branch of Tashkent Chemical-Technological University, this characteristic is also defined as “thematic specificity of use”. The term functions only in a certain professional field, is used by a limited circle of people - specialists in this field, employed in the framework of a certain special activity.

5. Conventionality and stylistic neutrality. The stylistic marking of a terminological unit is an undesirable component of its semantics, since carries additive shades of meaning that can distort the original conceptual charge of the term. Nevertheless, it is not uncommon for a term to acquire connotative shades, however, this phenomenon mainly takes place in the process of term determination and its use in an unusual context. In some cases, the meaning acquired by the term may have a marginal slang connotation.

6. Motivation. By this characteristic, we mean the relationship between the semantics of the term and its internal form, in other words, we mean a certain rational justification (from the point of view of logic) of the connection between content and form. In this case, it is also appropriate to talk about the application of the concept of “term orientation”, which is understood as “the property of the term, due to linguistic, mental and social factors, which gives the native speaker the opportunity to determine the concept assigned to the term or the place of this unit in the term system without resorting to the definition by the exponent». Partly to this characteristic, we tend to attach the function of the consistency of the semantics of the term.

Despite the fact that some scholars attribute nominativity to the main characteristics of the term, we are not inclined to consider this justified, because the nominative function is not a distinctive feature of the terms, it is characteristic of all nouns. Also optional characteristics, in our opinion, are euphony, internationality and modernity of terminological units.

The presence of these parameters is, of course, welcome in any terminological system, however, the absence of these characteristics does not lead to the restructuring of the term, and, therefore, they are not linguistically relevant.

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